

Empirical Analysis of Expected, Actual Waiting Time and Service Delivery: Evidence from Nigeria Hospitals.

Ramoni Tirimisiyu Amosa*, Illeladewa Adeoye Abiodun, Olorunlomeye Adam Biodun, Oni Esther Kemi & Oyetunji Olumayowa O

¹Department of Computer Science, School of Applied Sciences, Federal Polytechnic Ede, Osun State.

*Corresponding Author: ramoni.tirimisiyu@federalpolyede.edu.ng, +2348030695211

Abstract

Time, they say is a crucial, important and most expensive resources and waits for no one. The challenges of patients waiting endlessly to get served in a hospital has attracted attention from different researchers. Being the major, critical and fundamental factor for patients' satisfaction. Patient deserve to be able to predict the likely time he/she is likely to schedule for hospital visit especially for outpatient service. The research focus on determine the minimum and maximum time a patient may spend on the system using multi-channel queuing system (M/M/C) as this will help the patient to plan other schedules for the particular period of time. We collected data for two state hospital in different location through the personal observation approach. The data was collected for four working days (Monday to Friday) where the arrival and departure time for every patient was being monitored and average mean time method was adopted to determine the waiting time. Our findings reveal that hospital witness higher arrival rate on Monday being the first day of the week and also our result shows that expected minimum time for a patient is 35minutes 60 seconds while the expected maximum time the patient spent is 43minutes 20 seconds.

Keywords: Arrival, Departure, Hospital, Patients, Queue, Satisfaction.

Introduction

Patient injury and even death can occur from subpar service delivery. In order to improve the quality of the healthcare system, it is crucial to look at patient/client happiness (Kalwar et al, 2021). Service quality in healthcare facilities is a new phenomena, and many hospitals are worried about offering their patients high-quality care based on data gleaned from patient views of service quality (Mahmoud et al., 2019). The amount of time that a patient spends in the waiting area before the start of their appointment is considered to be their "waiting time" (Shanmugasundaram & Umarani, 2015). Reducing the amount of time that patients who are leaving the hospital have to wait is not only beneficial for the patients, but it also helps the hospital reduce the amount of work it has to do. Waiting time, which is seen as a significant aspect or variable in patient satisfaction, has garnered attention in the realm of providing services for health care. Long wait times are the source of many patients' complaints, and research has shown that this is the primary source of patient discontent with the delivery of medical care in outpatient clinics. Furthermore, it is a barrier for affected patients to make additional use of health care facilities. In outpatient facilities, it is common for patients to have to wait for a significant amount of time before being seen by a

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provider as Keeping patients waiting for longer than necessary can be stressful for both the patient and the attending physician (shen & Lee, 2018). This problem contributes to a variety of problems that affect public health, including impeded access to care, interruption of hospital work patterns, and dissatisfaction on the part of patients (Xie & Or, 2017). Since the issue of lengthy wait times continues to be a common challenge that can affect the level of satisfaction a patient has with their care, it seems important to gain a better understanding of how the factors of waiting times, service times, and patient satisfaction with care are related to one another Outpatient care can be divided into two distinct categories. One is the amount of time that has passed after the patient was referred by their primary care physician and has yet to attend their initial appointment. Another factor to consider is the amount of time that passes between a patient's arrival at the outpatient department and the time that they are allowed to enter the consulting room. For the purposes of this study, we did not bother to measure the amount of time spent in the waiting room by patient when entered the waiting room until all of the procedures leading up to being registered to see the doctor were completed. On the other hand, the amount of time spent waiting in the consultation room was measured from the moment the patient entered the consultation room until they were out after the history and examination was performed by the doctor.

Literature Review

Any country's residents must be in good health since healthy individuals can contribute to the growth of the national economy. The country's healthcare system is a significant industry that contributes significantly to the provision and maintenance of the general well-being of its population (Adeniran et al, 2022). Patient satisfaction remains the crucial factor in evaluating the quality of care and the performance of healthcare facilities (Umoke et al., 2020). Patient satisfaction remains the crucial factor in evaluating the quality of care and the performance of healthcare facilities. Individual patients may experience missed productivity, frustration, and dissatisfaction with the quality of care as a result of long wait times to visit their physicians (Oostrom et al., 2017). The amount of time that a patient must wait in the clinic before being attended to by a member of the clinic's medical staff is referred to as the waiting time. Patients view lengthy wait periods as a barrier to actually accessing the care they require, and holding patients waiting for longer than necessary can be a source of stress for both the patient and the treating physician Oche & Adamu, 2013). In the highly competitive world of the twenty-first century, any business or product that wants to expand and endure must be able to offer services and goods that can adapt to changing consumer demands. An organisation must offer high-quality services that can result in consumers' happiness and loyalty in order to obtain a competitive advantage (Mahmoud et al., 2019). Patients have a limited number of options, yet there is frequently poor communication between patients and medical staff, and occasionally the encounters between patients and medical staff are so bad that switching from one hospital to another or from one doctor to another becomes required (Adepoju, 2018). Despite the management's declining financing, the hospital is dealing with an increase in customer demand for improved patient satisfaction. To address this need, the hospital must critically assess how

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consumers perceive the quality of its services and use its limited resources. This is crucial given the recent reports of a few instances of poor quality of services in Nigeria (Aregbeshola, 2019), which pose a risk to the country's historically high patient satisfaction rating. A low patient satisfaction score could reflect poorly on the hospital (Mahmoud & Grigoriou, 2017). Patients' happiness and discontent with hospital facilities are influenced by the admission process, diagnostic services, technical services, communication and interpersonal way of the physicians, accessibility, and convenience ((Umoke et al., 2020; Hachem et al., 2021). Delivering healthcare services slowly is a key issue that receives a lot of attention in hospitals. This is because the queue system was poorly designed or was mismanaged. Inconsistencies in the medical system are caused by a lack of physicians and medications, and poor managerial practises extend beyond these crises (Khaskheli, 2020).

Research Methods

Data Collection

The data used for this research were collected from two different state hospitals; State hospital Ede and State hospital Ikire in Osun State, Nigeria through personal observation. We visited the two hospital to personally monitor and record the process physicians followed to attend to patients. Data collection were carried out from Monday to Thursday and within the working hours of 9:00am to 1:00 pm. The arrival and departure of outpatient were monitored and recorded every hour. Data collected were transformed into tabular form and were presented in table 1, table 2, table 3, table 4, and table 5 respectively. Two physicians (doctors) were selected in Ede state hospital label server 1 and server 2 and two physicians were also selected in Ikire state hospital labeled server 3 and server 4. All the doctors were attending to outpatients. In each of the hospitals, one central registration point was used, this means that any patient coming in to the hospital for medical care need to firstly visit the registration point either to get registered or for accessing and retrieving of his/her medical card or record. The time been spent at registration point were not monitored or captured during data collection, this was considered not necessary because each patient at reception were not for the same mission, its either a patient access his/her medical registration card or newly register as first timer, hence difference in time spent in registration point.

Base on the number of channel we have in this research work which is four channel (servers), it shows that server we have multiple server which prove that the system is multi-channel queuing system (M/M/C) and the following formula are to be considered in this research work:

λ = Average Arrival

μ = Average Departure

Waiting time for servers

$$\frac{Lq}{\lambda}$$

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$$\frac{\lambda^2}{\mu(\mu-\lambda)} \times \frac{1}{\lambda} = \frac{\lambda^2}{\mu(\mu-\lambda)\lambda} = \frac{\lambda}{\mu(\mu-\lambda)}$$

Waiting time for server

$$\frac{Lq}{\lambda} = \frac{\lambda}{\mu(\mu-\lambda)}$$

Average time spent in the server

$$\frac{\lambda^2}{\mu(\mu-\lambda)\lambda}$$

Results and Discussion

This section discuss various result in this research. It was observed from the data collected that the arrival rate between the hours of 9:00am and 10:00am is always high for all the days, the implication of this is that the patients prefer to go to hospital earlier so that they can be attended to as early as possible and also people. Also, the result of our findings shows that the arrival rate of the patient on Wednesdays and Thursday is low compare to Monday and Tuesday, the implication of this is that more people prefer to go to hospital early of the week as shown in figure 1.

Table 1: Arrival and Departure Time for Day1 (Monday)

Table 1 show the Arrival and Departure time of the patients in the hospital for Day 1 with their respective servers.

	Server 1		Server 2		Server 3		Server 4	
	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure
9:00am – 10:00am	29	20	17	21	15	13	22	20
10:00am – 11:00am	25	27	16	19	13	09	13	14
11:00am – 12:00pm	17	20	20	21	11	11	19	09
12:00pm – 1:00pm	08	10	09	11	09	01	08	10
1:00pm – 2:00pm	03	08	02	00	01	06	03	04

Table 1 shows the number of patients in the queue with the stated time for each server arrival departure for 4 servers from 9:00am to 2:00pm for the first day.

Table 2: Arrival and Departure Time for Day2 (Tuesday)

Table 2 shows the arrival and departure time of the patients the hospital for Day 2 with their respective servers.

	Server 1		Server 2		Server 3		Server 4	
	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure
9:00am – 10:00am	31	19	19	20	13	12	20	22
10:00am – 11:00am	25	23	13	15	12	10	05	11
11:00am – 12:00pm	19	17	15	16	11	08	09	12
12:00pm – 1:00pm	04	12	09	11	09	09	11	05
1:00pm – 2:00pm	03	08	07	02	01	07	07	07

Table 2 shows the number of patient in the queue with the stated time for each server arrival and departure for 4 servers from 9:00am to 2:00pm for the second day.

Table 3: Arrival and Departure Time for Day3 (Wednesday)

Table 3 shows the arrival and departure time of the patients in the hospital for Day 3 with their respective servers.

	Server 1		Server 2		Server 3		Server 4	
	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure
9:00am – 10:00am	15	13	13	17	10	12	15	17
10:00am – 11:00am	17	15	11	15	07	10	13	15
11:00am – 12:00pm	15	13	14	17	09	11	12	11

12:00pm 1:00pm	–	05	08	08	09	05	06	09	09
1:00pm 2:00pm	–	01	06	07	00	01	04	02	05

Table 4 shows the numbers of patients in the queue with the stated time for each server (arrival and departure) for 3 servers from 9:00am to 2:00pm for the third day.

Table 4: Arrival and Departure Time for Day4 (Thursday)

This table shows the arrival and departure time of the patients on day 4 for all the servers.

	Server 1		Server 2		Server 3		Server 4		
	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	Arrival	Departure	
9:00am 10:00am	–	11	10	09	13	06	10	09	08
10:00am 11:00am	–	08	09	11	08	10	09	10	11
11:00am 12:00pm	–	11	10	11	12	07	06	12	09
12:00pm 1:00pm	–	04	06	07	05	03	05	03	07
1:00pm 2:00pm	–	01	06	08	02	01	03	00	05

Table 5: Average Arrival and departure of people in the system.

Table 5 shows the Average arrival and departure of people in the system

Days	Server 1		Server 2		Server 3		Server 2	
	Arrival (λ)	Departure (μ)	Arrival (λ)	Departure (μ)	Arrival (λ)	Departure (μ)	Arrival (λ)	Departure (μ)
Day 1	16.4	17.0	12.8	14.4	9.8	8.0	13.0	16.4
Day 2	16.4	15.8	12.6	12.8	9.2	9.2	10.4	14.2

Day 3	10.6	11.0	10.6	11.6	6.4	8.6	10.2	12.0
Day 4	7.0	8.2	9.2	8.0	5.4	6.6	6.8	7.8
Total Average Arrival and Departure	50.4	52.0	45.2	46.8	30.8	32.4	40.4	50.41

Table 5 above shows the average arrival (λ) and departure (μ) for day 1, 2, 3, 4 with total average arrival and departure for each servers

* Waiting time of each Server

$$q = \frac{\lambda}{\mu} \text{ --- Average Arrival}$$

$$\mu \text{ --- Average Departure}$$

Figure 1: Average Arrival Rate for four days

Figure 1: The Chart above is the Multiple bar Chart that shows the Average arrival rate for each patients for four days.

Table 6: Waiting Time for Servers

Table 6 below shows the waiting time for servers in the queue.

	Server 1	Server 2	Server 3	Server 4
Average Arrival (λ)	50.4	45.2	30.8	40.4
Average Departure (μ)	52.0	46.8	32.4	42.2

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Waiting Time for each Server (q)	0.97	0.97	0.95	0.96
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The table 6 above shows that the average that the average arrival rate (λ) server 1 is 50.4 for server 2 is 45.2 and server 3 is 30.8 and for server 4 is 40.4, Average departure (μ) for server 1 is 52.0 for server 2 is 46.8 for server 3 is 32.4 and for server 4 is 42.2 while waiting time for each server: for server 1 0.97 for server 2 0.97 for server 3 0.95 for server 4 is 0.96 as it was stated on the table above

*Average number of people present in the server

$$L = \frac{q}{1-q}$$

Table 7: Average Number of People in the Server

Table 7 below shows the Average Number of people in the server

	Server 1	Server 2	Server 3	Server 4
Waiting Time (q)	0.97	0.97	0.95	0.96
1-q	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.04
Average Number of People (L)	32.33	32.33	19.00	24.00

The table 7 above shows that the waiting time for server 1 is 0.97 for server 2 is 0.97 for server 3 is 0.95 for server 4 is 0.96.

The probability that the patient will be delayed by server 1 is 0.03 by server 2 is 0.03, by server 3 is 0.05 and by server 4 is 0.04 while the expected number of people in the system for server 1 is 32.33 for server 2 is 32.33 for server 3 is 19.00 for server 4 is 24.00

* Average time spent in the server

$$W = \frac{L}{\lambda}$$

Table 8

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The table 8 below shows the average time spent in the system

Server A1	Server A2	Server B1	Server B2
<u>32.33</u> 50.40	<u>32.33</u> 45.20	<u>19.00</u> 30.8	<u>24.00</u> 40.40
0.64hours	0.72hours	0.62hours	0.59hours
38.40minutes	43.20minutes	37.00minutes	35.60minutes

Table 8 above shows that average time spent in the system by each patient are: sever 1 is 38 minutes 49 seconds, server 2 is 43 minutes 20 seconds 3 is 37 minutes while server 4 is 35 minutes 60 seconds

Average time spent by 4 server.

$$= \frac{38.4 + 43.2 + 37.0 + 35.6}{4} = 38.55 \text{ minutes}$$

Total time spent on the server = 38.55minutes

Conclusion

This research work consider two different hospital and considered multichannel system. Patients are unhappy because of the average time spent in the system before they are answered. Base on the analysis above, it show that minimum average time the patient used is 35minutes 60 seconds while the maximum time the patient spent is 43minutes 20 seconds.

Recommendation

Base on the summary and conclusion of this study, the following recommendation were made for satisfaction of the patients:

1. The Osun state hospital management board should adopt a three or four servicing point for each state hospital in Ede and Ikire to reduce the time spend by the patients.
2. The method of first come first serve should be adopt by the Doctors to the patients.
3. There should be proper monitor of the staff (Doctors, Nurses, Administrative Officers e.t.c) for proper and smooth running of the hospital.

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